

Impact of Alcoholism of Partner on the Mental Health of Women: Findings from an Exploratory Research

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ABSTRACT: Alcoholism is a pervasive phenomenon. Many wives around the world have endured decades of suffering from husbands who abuse their wives and children when they get home drunk. Remarkably, the majority of women stay away from expressing their disapproval and instead timidly adapt to their husbands' behaviors. The present investigation is part of the attempt to understand the factors influencing mental health of women in Kerala. The study was conducted in two phases. In the first phase a quantitative survey among 300 women to assess the mental health status of women was conducted. Fifty women, 25 each with the highest and lowest mental health scores in the survey were selected for the second phase of the study. The factors influencing mental health of women were explored using in depth unstructured interviews with the 50 women followed by thematic analysis. This study clearly demonstrates how alcohol consumption by husbands has an impact on women, their kids, and families as a whole. Women who live with alcoholic husbands have heavy mental stress and they face several forms of economic, emotional, sexual and physical violence in their day to day lives.

KEYWORDS: Alcoholism, Violence Against Women, Mental Health, Domestic Violence, Sexual Abuse

INTRODUCTION

Alcoholism is a pervasive phenomenon. Women and children endure various forms of suffering from an alcoholic member in the family. The majority of women stay away from expressing their disapproval or open up their traumatic experiences out of fear of women blaming from the kinship and the general society. Even while alcoholism is mostly discussed in the context of the individual, the family as a whole is impacted. Every family member suffers when there is one alcohol user since it leads to strife and disturbances in the family. Alcoholism has such a deep impact on families that it eventually causes the family to break apart as a unit. Various negative emotional states, such as shame, guilt, fear, anger, loneliness and sadness and are frequently reported by the family members of alcoholics (Saha & Sharma, 2016). Of all the members, alcoholic wives suffer the most because of the severe trauma and stress they experience in their homes, which leads to serious psychological issues in them. The high levels of poor self-esteem, depression, anxiety and neuroticism are a few of the symptoms on the slope (Lander et al., 2013). The three most prevalent and well-known issues that women of alcoholics deal with are economic, emotional, and domestic violence. Furthermore, the alcoholic is unable to fulfil his expected roles and obligations because he is so consumed with alcohol that he ignores the needs and circumstances of other family members (Sharma et al., 2016). In such a scenario, the functions that are normally carried by husbands often fall on the wives, further adding to their burden and suffering (Satyanarayana et al., 2010).

The adoption of the Sustainable Development Goals 2030 agenda enhanced the international mandate to limit alcohol's harmful consumption (SDG 2030). It is commonly known that lowering alcohol consumption harm will help advance the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by achieving a number of its objectives. SDG 1 (ending poverty), SDG 4 (quality education), SDG 5 (gender equality), SDG 8 (decent work and economic growth), SDG 10 (reducing disparities between and within nations), and SDG 16 (peace, justice, and strong institutions) are among the targets covered by this. Effectively reducing the harmful use of alcohol will significantly contribute to the achievement of good health and well-being globally (SDG 3), given the detrimental effects of alcohol consumption on the development and outcomes of many diseases and health conditions, including major Non-Communicable Diseases (NCDs) and injuries. Moreover, improving the prevention and treatment of substance abuse, particularly problematic alcohol use, is a goal of SDG 3's Target 5. This illustrates how alcohol abuse has a negative influence on health in areas other than non-communicable diseases (NCDs) and mental health (SDG Target 3.4); they include road traffic accidents (SDG 3.6), reproductive health (SDG 3.7), universal health coverage (3.8), and infectious illnesses (SDG 3.3) (WHO 2021, p. 4). The 7th Global Alcohol Policy Conference, which took place in Cape Town, South Africa in 2023, recognised that alcohol consumption is a major cause of global illness and the primary obstacle to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals.

Impact of Alcoholism of Partner on the Mental Health of Women: Findings from an Exploratory Research

As stated by the WHO (2021), the impact of the harmful use of alcohol on health and well-being is not limited to health consequences alone. Alcohol abuse incurs significant social and economic losses relating to costs in the justice sector (Mares et al., 2013; Mulia, 2014), costs from lost workforce productivity and unemployment (Dryden, 2022; Schou & Inger, 2016), and costs assigned to pain and suffering (Rehm, 2011; Stanesby, 2018). The harmful use of alcohol can also result in harm to others, such as family members, friends, co-workers and strangers (Dale et al., 2010; Greenfield, 2015; Laslett, 2013; Sharma et al., 2016). Among the most dramatic manifestations of harm to persons other than drinkers are road traffic injuries (Lasota et al., 2020; Nasueb, 2022; Stewart et al., 2012) and consequences of prenatal alcohol exposure that may result in the development of fetal alcohol spectrum disorders (FASD) (Kaminen-Ahola, 2020; Mattson et al., 2019; Popova et al., 2023; Wozniak et al., 2019). “The harms to others may be very tangible, specific and time-bound (e.g. injuries or damage) or may be less tangible and result from suffering, poor health and well-being, and the social consequences of drinking (e.g. being harassed or insulted, or feeling threatened)” (WHO, 2021, p.2).

Alcoholism of Partner and Violence Against Women

In the light of previous studies, Flanzer (1993) points out that Alcohol acts as a situational element, lowering inhibitions, affecting judgement, and making it harder for people to recognise cues, all of which increase the risk of violence. The person is more likely to perpetrate sexual offences if he has additional morbidities such as antisocial and delusional personality disorder, paranoid schizophrenia, and bipolar illness. Numerous forensic cases in India, including those involving Bobbit, Manu Sharma, Nirbhaya, and others, have shown evidence that alcohol was a regular factor in crimes against women (Sharma et al., 2016). McCauley et al. (1995) conclude that alcohol has consistently emerged as a risk marker for partner violence that is especially consistent across a range of settings. The most highly reported consequences of partner's alcoholism are the emotional problems, the least reported are the problems of physical violence (Govindappa & Pankajakshi, 2014; Sharma et al., 2016; Sreekumar et al., 2016). Partner's alcohol consumption increases women's likelihood of experiencing emotional, sexual and physical violence (Aboagye, 2022; Sontate et al., 2021).

Women are reported to be twice as likely to experience physical abuse, including potentially fatal injuries, as a result of alcohol-related domestic violence (Ferrari, 2018; Galbicsek, 2020; Myshak et al., 2020).

The Covid 19 pandemic situation, which required an extended stay at home atmosphere has triggered increased alcohol consumption among men, with rising tension leading to the use of unwanted violence, which has been reported based on an average one-third increase in calls to helplines (UN Women, 2020). The National Commission for Women (NCW) and many states mentioned an increase in domestic violence cases during lockdown (Vora et al., 2020). Lockdowns and instructions to stay at home have aggravated domestic violence that is linked to drinking too much alcohol. According to the WHO (2021), one in three children encounter violence from parents or other family members, and nearly one in three women will have experienced sexual or physical abuse at the hands of an intimate partner at some point in their lives. On the other hand, because alcohol was unavailable during Covid-19, many people suffered from alcohol withdrawal symptoms (Ahmed et al., 2020; Verma, 2020) which in turn also have negatively impacted the families.

Continuous alcohol use and related violence not only affects the individual but also family members, especially the spouse/ wives who faces many emotional and psychological problems and stressful life events (Pathath & Begum, 2022). The problems faced by alcoholics' wives are in multiple domains like social, physical and emotional. Jeyaseelan et al. (2007) found that regular use of alcohol by the husband has been strongly associated with low mental health of women. Intimate partner violence resulting from alcohol abuse of husband causes serious mental illness in women (Babu & Car, 2010). Study reports reveals that individuals who are married to persons dependent on alcohol have low overall physical and mental health (Pathath et al., 2018). Dostanic (2022) concludes that the mental health of women whose partners have alcohol addicts is significantly threatened and should be considered, especially when it is connected with exposure to spousal violence. Women's experiences of abuse, degree of fear, and perception of safety are significantly influenced by their partner's alcohol consumption (Wilson et al., 2020).

Background of the Study

India was one of the fastest-growing markets for alcohol until the COVID-19 pandemic after which a nearly 12% decline in consumption was noticed as per the National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5) Report published in 2019–20. Yet, while in 164 countries heavy episodic drinking has decreased and remained steady in recent years, India is one of the 16 where it has increased (Ray, 2023). The alcohol consumption rates are so high in India and it has been identified as the third biggest market for alcoholic beverages in the world (Statista, 2023; The Election Budget, 2023). The drinking patterns of Indians indicate that they do not drink for enjoyment or socialising, but rather to get intoxicated (Ray, 2023). With regard to the Indian state of Kerala, among those aged 15 to 49, alcohol consumption was reported by 1.6% of women and 37% of males in the NFHS-4 Report of 2015–16. It has declined to 19.9% of men and 0.2% of women as per the NFHS 5 Report of 2019-20. Despite the different target age range, a comparison of the two reports reveals a 46% decrease in the number of customers, but the alcohol consumption rate of the state is still higher than the national average.

However, according to a report of The New Indian Express (2023) based on information received through RTI, the exchequer gained over Rs 35,000 crore in wealth in Kerala is from spirits sales during the first two years of the current government. Kerala sold 41.68

Impact of Alcoholism of Partner on the Mental Health of Women: Findings from an Exploratory Research

crore litres of Indian Made Foreign Liquor (IMFL) between May 2021 and May 2023. In addition, between May 2021 and May 2023, the State Beverages Corporation (Bevco) sold 16.67 crore litres of wine and beer. Liquor sales are on the rise in Kerala around festivals like Onam, Christmas, and New Year in recent years. The Kerala State Beverages Corporation (BEVCO) reports that the state saw an unprecedented record-breaking alcohol sale of over Rs 100 crore on the New Year's Eve (Business Standard, 2023) and during the ten-day Onam harvest festival it reached a record high of Rs 759 crore, up roughly Rs 60 crore from the previous year (Abraham, 2023).

A cross-sectional study conducted in the Indian state of Kerala, with spouses of males with alcohol addiction who were enrolled in a de-addiction programme, found a strong relationship between the number of stressful events in the previous year and the length of marriage and the incidence of domestic violence (Indu et al., 2018). However, Valasseri and Kuruvilla (2018) in their attempt to analyse the causal factors of increasing domestic violence cases in Kerala, examined 150 cases that have been reported under the Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005 (PWDVA, 2005). The study reveals that the primary causes of domestic violence in Kerala continue to be dowry demands and alcohol addiction of male partners.

The Indian Psychological Association warns against the poorer mental health of women in the state of Kerala when compared to their counterparts, despite their commendable performance and higher standing in various developmental indicators such as infant and maternal mortality rates, literacy rates, and other relevant benchmarks. This stark contrast in their mental well-being has prompted the analysis focused on mental health of Keralite women vis-a vis the high alcohol consumption rate in the state.

METHOD

The present investigation is part of the attempt to understand the factors influencing mental health of women in Kerala. Ethical clearance for the present study was obtained from the Calicut University Ethics Committee for Human Research. The researcher collected informed consent from the participants and clarified their doubts about the study. The ASHA (Accredited Social Health Activists) and Anganwadi workers (ICDS- Integrated Child Development Services) who facilitated the recruitment of study participants were also given detailed information about the study, its objectives and requirements so as to be conveyed to the respondents. The study was conducted in two phases. In the first phase a quantitative survey to assess the mental health status of women was conducted. WHO (ten) Wellbeing Index was administered on a representative sample of 300 married women belonging to southern, central and northern districts of Kerala. Since Kerala is a state with high literacy and educational standards for women, the WHO questionnaire was completed by the respondents themselves. Fifty women, 25 each with the highest and lowest mental health scores in the first phase were selected as the High Mental Health (High MH) Group and Low Mental Health (Low MH) group respectively for the second phase of the qualitative exploratory study. The factors influencing mental health of women were explored using in depth unstructured interviews with the 50 study participants followed by thematic analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the quantum of data generated through interviews, alcoholism of partner was found to be a prominent factor that has a negative toll on women's mental health. Lived experiences of women as narrated by them are highlighted to reveal the gravity of the situation they go through in everyday life. A striking finding in this context was that women in the High MH group also were facing similar issues as that of the women in Low MH group but much variations were found in the number of study participants experiencing the same among the two groups. The frequency of incidents, gravity of experience and the approach of participants to the incidents varied much in the High and Low MH groups. The major incidents related to alcoholism of partners as shared by the study participants are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Incidents Related to Alcoholism of Partner

Alcoholism of Partner	Low MH	High MH
Excessive drinking	20	0
Children's studies getting affected	20	0
Physical abuse	18	1
Verbal abuse	25	22
Economic debts	19	2
Sexual abuse and perverted sex	19	4
Alienation from kins and society	16	0

Source: Primary data

Twenty women from the Low MH group claimed that alcoholism of their spouses was a significant factor that destroys their peace and happiness. Children experience problems such as social marginalization and academic difficulties as a result of their father's alcoholism, which have far reaching impacts on the kids at home. Due to their alcoholic nature, women are found to develop several physical and psychological disorders.

In relationships with alcoholic partners, verbal abuse such as using insulting comments towards women and their families is frequent.

Impact of Alcoholism of Partner on the Mental Health of Women: Findings from an Exploratory Research

Twenty women concurred that their drunken husbands verbally abuse them. They all conveyed that if they dare to question the husband about his regular drinking, he would lose his temper and insult their dignity.

36-year-old Bindu who is from a middle-class Hindu family said,

"My husband creates problems with our children, and they are fearful every day. My husband had doubts about my son because he was not of his complexion. Once the child was beaten by him whereby, he fell down which caused it to lose a lot of blood from head and my child became unconscious. Following this incident, the police, other social workers, and neighbors all stepped in to help resolve the problems. He is both my spouse and the father of my children, so I did not file a complaint against him. He upsets the family only when he is intoxicated."

The spouses of Keralite women, especially alcoholic husbands, seem to be motivated by such thoughts that wives wouldn't file any complaint against their children's father.

The study participants with alcoholic husbands confessed that having a husband for namesake protects them from harassment and sexual assault of the public. 36-year-old Muslim woman, Sumaya from a middle-class family shared an incident of how her husband was dropped off at the house by friends late at night, that he was undressed, and that she found him in the yard.

"I accompanied him to the bathroom where I pour water on his head. But as soon as he awakens, he asks me, "Who the hell are you to look after me?" Members of the Mahal committee have frequently told him not to drink in their community. He started drinking daily after disobeying them. I felt helpless as I looked at the faces of my children because sometimes there isn't anything in the house to cook. What should I do? I am unemployed and have only primary education. We currently live in a house near the mosque arranged by the Mahal committee." Women's conditions are terrible, and they are powerless to leave these unhealthy and irresponsible marriages. With motherhood, the women struggle to raise the children and later on the mother and children together battle to survive. Though social drinking is becoming far more acceptable in the society, the problem of drinking is often viewed as stigmatic. Thus, the family members of alcoholic participants often feel estranged and are looked down upon by others. In this study, women with alcoholic husbands reported feeling ashamed in society. This leads to a marked reduction in social engagements. As reported by Parsakarathy (2015), the wives of alcoholic husbands in the study also reported general social dysfunction.

Women experience much social discrimination, and women and kids are stigmatized as the wives and children of drunkards. Rajitha, a 36-year-old Hindu middle-class woman is worried that her son frequently raises the issue of being called the son of an alcoholic by his friends. The kids suffer the loss of self-esteem and confidence and become marginalized by society. Because all children have the right to a safe and happy childhood up until the age of 18, and because their parents have a responsibility to support and care for them, this situation is extremely dangerous. However, an alcoholic environment is hardly a peaceful environment, and the kids do not receive any support or attention from their parents. Every other day, the children witness their mothers' tears. It will have an impact on their thoughts, making them uncontrollable and disinterested in studies. In the present study, 13 women in the Low MH group shared similar stories. However, the effects of a husband's alcoholism extend beyond the wife to the kids and the family structure as a whole.

32-year-old Shyni from a lower-class Hindu family shared that her drunken husband regularly violates her sexually. When she refuses to let him, he beats her and performs some pornographic sex. Elsa, 33-year-old respondent from a high-class Christian family also said that her husband uses some instruments in her vagina, and due to this, she has some physical issues and her uterus was removed. She is currently being abused by her husband and family, who claim she is incapable of bearing children. She believes her husband to be responsible for her present condition, as he still curses her. His family supports him, and they force him to divorce her.

Dhanya from a wealthy Hindu family explained how her husband regularly consumes alcohol and frequently takes advantage of her sexually,

"After drinking, he craves my company in bed and tries out novel sexual actions on me. Initially, I was unaffected by this, but later on he started forcing me into doing everything he desired. I experience daily discomfort from vaginal infections and was scared to discuss this with a doctor. I hate his pornographic and unnatural sexual acts but he always does the same. If I talk about this to anyone, what would they think?"

Fifteen women in the Low MH Group shared how they all keep quiet and put up with their alcoholic husbands' sexual exploitation. Due to fear of what other people may think, the women are not ready to discuss issues relating to their sexuality with anyone. Patriarchy has a big part to play in why sex and sexuality are still taboo subjects in women's lives. Women who discuss foreplay and contraceptives are accused of being prostitutes or of not being virgins. Virginity plays a significant role in Indian women's lives. Women are expected to be unaware of sex and sexuality; they are supposed to know about sex after being married, which is the traditional concept in Indian society.

Sindhu from a lower-class Hindu family once ran out from her house due to her husband's abuse and went to the police station at midnight. She opened up,

"He kicked me in the abdomen, pulled my hair, and threw me against the wall. When he drinks, he always behaves in this manner. His cruel attitude and actions killed our son. Once he hit him and my child fell on his head, and passed away because the injury was

Impact of Alcoholism of Partner on the Mental Health of Women: Findings from an Exploratory Research

so severe. I felt incredibly sad and depressed after that, but he maintains the same attitude. He still abuses me while drunk.”

It is difficult for many women to survive with their alcoholic husbands. If at all a woman files a complaint against the husband, she is compelled to compromise and go with the alcoholic husband by the police. Their propensity for settling issues push women back into violent relationships. Nothing has changed about the concept that women should endure all forms of abuse in relationships. All the human rights that apply to women get violated while the husbands are alcoholics.

There are alcoholic husbands in the High MH group also, but lesser violence was reported by the study participants in the group. The husbands were reported to act maturely and make sure not to disturb anyone, especially their wives. Clara, 34-year-old from a wealthy Christian household says,

“I enjoy having sex with him when he is drunk. he is more lovable and conversing with him at that time is enjoyable.”

Another Hindu woman from a middle-class family stated she likes her husband's drunken behavior. She claims that because there is no longer any physical, mental, or sexual abuse, she loves the husband's behavior when he drinks. Furthermore, drinking is under control and not excessive. They are more conscious of their neighbors and society, which is why they control themselves to be not known outside.

Alcoholism is a significant factor influencing the mental health status of women in Kerala. Several studies substantiate the present finding that the wives of alcoholics undergo intense trauma and stress in their household environment, which brings about major mental health problems in them (Satyanarayana et al., 2010). The high levels of depression, neuroticism, anxiety and poor self-esteem are a few of the symptoms on the slope (Lander et al., 2013). Domestic violence, economic violence and emotional violence are the most frequently occurring and well-recognized problems faced by the wives of alcoholics (Dostanic, 2022; Sharma, 2022; UN Women, 2020). Children may struggle academically and face ridicule from their peers, while women may experience feelings of sadness, stress, alienation and helplessness. The family is an integral part of the larger community system, and substance abuse by a family member can disrupt the balance of the family structure.

The state of Kerala has the discredit of having a higher alcohol consumption rate than the national average. Despite the violence and associated trauma, the study participants continue to stay back in the abusive relationship with husbands as most of them are economically dependent on the husbands and have no place to go. In the patrilocal culture of the state, married women are least welcome in their natal homes. Without any fallback options they live a life for their children. The learned helplessness proposed by Walker (1977) is fully applicable in the case of study participants with husbands who are regular consumers of liquor.

Twenty women with alcoholic husbands shared how their husbands sexually exploit them and how the issues created due to alcoholism affect the whole family, especially the children. 36-year-old Rajitha asserts how women face social exclusion and the children also face some peer teasing when their father is a drunkard. Nobody is ready to talk about sexual exploitation because it is still a taboo.

CONCLUSION

To gain support for a more rapid implementation of the Global plan, decision-makers and the general public must be made aware of the harm caused by alcohol and the efficacy of policy measures through strategic and well-developed worldwide communication and advocacy. As exhorted by WHO (2021), to mobilise all stakeholders for coordinated steps to preserve public health and promote widespread political commitment to reduce the harmful use of alcohol, special initiatives and activities are required. The present research is an initiative in this regard to expose the deplorable conditions, helplessness and sufferings undergone by wives of alcoholic husbands.

Women's mental health is significantly compromised for government profit because there is no effective government regulation on the sale of alcohol in the state. Violence against women can be reduced to a great extent if alcohol sales are properly regulated. This study clearly demonstrates how drinking by husbands has an impact on women, kids, and families. The study recommends that governments should take decisive action to regulate alcohol distribution and address alcoholism-related violence against women. This may include stricter alcohol control measures and effective law enforcement to protect women from harm. The true spirit of “Investing in People before Profit”, the thrust of the Global Alcohol Policy Conference, Cape Town, South Africa 2023 is to be accepted by all states to attain Target 3.5 of the Sustainable Development Goal 3 that attempts to improve substance abuse treatment and prevention, including unsafe alcohol use.

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REFERENCES

- 1) Aboagye, R. G., Ahinkorah, B. O., Tengan, C. L., Salifu, I., Acheampong, H. Y., & Seidu, A. A. (2022). Partner alcohol consumption and intimate partner violence against women in sexual unions in sub-Saharan Africa. *PloS One*, 17(12),

Impact of Alcoholism of Partner on the Mental Health of Women: Findings from an Exploratory Research

e0278196. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0278196>

- 2) Abraham, B. (2023, August 31). Onam 2023: Kerala partied with all-time high liquor sale worth Rs 759 crore in ten days. <https://www.indiatimes.com/news/india/onam-2023-kerala-soled-rs-759-crore-worth-liquor-in-ten-days-613671.html>. Accessed on 18.11.2023.
- 3) Ahmed, S., Khaium, M. O., & Tazmeem, F. (2020). COVID-19 lockdown in India triggers a rapid rise in suicides due to the alcohol withdrawal symptoms: Evidence from media reports. *The International Journal of Social Psychiatry*, 66(8), 827–829. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0020764020938809>
- 4) Babu, B.V. & Kar, S.K. (2010). Domestic violence in eastern India: Factors associated with victimization and perpetration. *Public Health*, 124 (3), 136-48, doi:10.1016/j.puhe.2010.01.014
- 5) Business Standard (2023). All-time liquor sale in Kerala on a high during New Year eve: BevCo. https://www.business-standard.com/article/current-affairs/all-time-liquor-sale-in-kerala-on-a-high-during-new-year-eve-bevco-123010100720_1.html accessed on 12.12.2023
- 6) Dale, C. E., & Livingston, M. J. (2010). The burden of alcohol drinking on co-workers in the Australian workplace. *The Medical journal of Australia*, 193(3), 138–140. <https://doi.org/10.5694/j.1326-5377.2010.tb03831.x>
- 7) Dostanic, N., Djikanovic, B., Jovanovic, M., Stamenkovic, Z., & Đeric, A. (2022). The Association Between Family Violence, Depression and Anxiety Among Women Whose Partners Have Been Treated for Alcohol Dependence. *Journal of family violence*, 37(2), 313–324. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10896-020-00238-1>
- 8) Dryden, J. (2022 March, 17). In U.S., Alcohol Use Disorder Linked to 232 Million Missed Workdays Annually, *Washington University School of Medicine in St. Louis*. <https://medicine.wustl.edu/news/in-u-s-alcohol-use-disorder-linked-to-232-million-missed-workdays-annually/> accessed on 13.12.23
- 9) Ferrari, G., Agnew-Davies, R., Bailey, J., Howard, L., Howarth, E., Peters, T. J., Sardinha, L., & Feder, G. S. (2016). Domestic violence and mental health: a cross-sectional survey of women seeking help from domestic violence support services. *Global health action*, 9, 29890. <https://doi.org/10.3402/gha.v9.29890>
- 10) Flanzer, J.P. (1993). *Alcohol and Other Drugs are Key Causal Agents of Violence*,” In: Gelles RJ, Loseke DR, editors. *Current Controversies on Family Violence*. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE, 171-81. doi:10.4135/9781483328584.n10
- 11) Galbicsek, C. (2020). *Alcohol-Related Crimes*. <https://www.alcoholrehabguide.org/alcohol/crimes/> accessed on 15.10.2023
- 12) Global Alcohol Policy Alliance, (2023). Successful GAPC 2023 held in Cape Town, <https://globalgapa.org/events/gapc-2023-cape-town/> accessed on 15.12.2023.
- 13) Govindappa, L, & Pankajakshi, B. (2014). A community study on wives of alcoholics. *DPS*. 17, 323– 27, <http://www.medind.nic.in/daa/t14/i2/daat14i2p323.pdf>
- 14) Greenfield, T. K., Karriker-Jaffe, K. J., Kaplan, L. M., Kerr, W. C., & Wilsnack, S. C. (2015). Trends in alcohol's harms to others (AHTO) and co-occurrence of family-related AHTO: The Four US National Alcohol Surveys, 2000-2015. *Substance Abuse: Research and Treatment*, 9(2), 23–31. <https://doi.org/10.4137/SART.S23505>
- 15) Indu, P. V., Jinu, C. R., Pallikkal, N. R., Sampathkumar, R., & Joy, J. (2018). Experience of domestic violence and psychological morbidity in spouses of alcohol-dependent males. *Indian Journal of Psychological Medicine*, 40(4), 322–327. https://doi.org/10.4103/IJPSYM.IJPSYM_38_18
- 16) Jeyaseelan, L., Kumar, S., Neelakantan, N., Peedicayil, A., Pillai, R., & Duvvury, N. (2007). Physical spousal violence against women in India: Some risk factors. *Journal of Biosocial Science*, 39(5), 657–670. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0021932007001836>
- 17) Kaminen-Ahola N. (2020). Fetal alcohol spectrum disorders: Genetic and epigenetic mechanisms. *Prenatal Diagnosis*, 40(9), 1185–1192. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pd.5731>
- 18) Lander, L., Howsare, J., & Byrne, M. (2013). The impact of substance use disorders on families and children: from theory to practice. *Social Work in Public Health*, 28(3-4), 194–205. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19371918.2013.759005>
- 19) Laslett, A.-M., Callinan, S. and Pennay, A. (2013), The increasing significance of alcohol's harm to others research. *Drugs and Alcohol Today*, Vol. 13 No. 3, pp. 163-172. <https://doi.org/10.1108/DAT-11-2012-0010>
- 20) Lasota, D., Al-Wathinani, A., Krajewski, P., Goniewicz, K., & Pawłowski, W. (2020). Alcohol and road accidents involving pedestrians as unprotected road users. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(23), 8995. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17238995>
- 21) Mares, S. H., Lichtwarck-Aschoff, A., & Engels, R. C. (2013). Intergenerational transmission of drinking motives and how they relate to young adults' alcohol use. *Alcohol and Alcoholism (Oxford, Oxfordshire)*, 48(4), 445–451. <https://doi.org/10.1093/alcalc/agt025>
- 22) Mattson, S. N., Bernes, G. A., & Doyle, L. R. (2019). Fetal alcohol spectrum disorders: A review of the neurobehavioral

Impact of Alcoholism of Partner on the Mental Health of Women: Findings from an Exploratory Research

- deficits associated with prenatal alcohol exposure. *Alcoholism, Clinical and Experimental Research*, 43(6), 1046–1062. <https://doi.org/10.1111/acer.14040>
- 23) Mayshak, R., Curtis, A., Coomber, K., Tonner, L., Walker, A., Hyder, S., Liknaitzky, P., & Miller, P. (2022). Alcohol-involved family and domestic violence reported to police in Australia. *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*, 37(3-4), NP1658–NP1685. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260520928633>
- 24) McCauley, J., Kern, D. E., Kolodner, K., Dill, L., Schroeder, A. F., DeChant, H. K., Ryden, J., Bass, E. B., & Derogatis, L. R. (1995). The "battering syndrome": prevalence and clinical characteristics of domestic violence in primary care internal medicine practices. *Annals of Internal Medicine*, 123(10), 737–746. <https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-123-10-199511150-00001>
- 25) Mulia, N., Zemore, S. E., Murphy, R., Liu, H., & Catalano, R. (2014). Economic loss and alcohol consumption and problems during the 2008 to 2009 U.S. recession. *Alcoholism, Clinical and Experimental Research*, 38(4), 1026–1034. <https://doi.org/10.1111/acer.12301>
- 26) Nasueb, S., Jankhotkaew, J., Vichitkunakorn, P., & Waleewong, O. (2022). The association among alcohol consumption patterns, drink-driving behaviors, and the harm from alcohol-related road traffic injuries due to the drinking of others in Thailand. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(23), 16281. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph192316281>
- 27) Parsakarathy, K. (2015). *Psychosocial problems of wives of alcoholics*. *IJSR The Global Journals*, 2, 574-575.
- 28) Pathath, A. W. & Begum, N. (2022). Parental alcoholism and subjective well-being of their children in Kerala. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 10(4), 856-860. DIP:18.01.083.20221004, DOI:10.25215/1004.083
- 29) Pathath, A. W., Begum, N., & Ali, S. I. (2018). Alcoholism among Husbands and Its Psychological Impact on wives in Malappuram District. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 6(4), 62-65. DIP:18.01.048/20180604, DOI:10.25215/0604.048
- 30) Popova, S., Charness, M. E., Burd, L., Crawford, A., Hoyme, H. E., Mukherjee, R. A. S., Riley, E. P., & Elliott, E. J. (2023). Fetal alcohol spectrum disorders. *Nature Reviews. Disease Primers*, 9(1), 11. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41572-023-00420-x>
- 31) Ray, K. (2023, February 9). Consumer Body Seeks Curbs as India's Per capital Alcohol Intake Doubles, *Deccan Herald*. <https://www.deccanherald.com/india/consumer-body-seeks-curbs-as-indias-per-capital-alcohol-intake-doubles-1189689.html> accessed on 10.11.2023.
- 32) Rehm J. (2011). The risks associated with alcohol use and alcoholism. *Alcohol Research & Health: The Journal of the National Institute on Alcohol Abuse and Alcoholism*, 34(2), 135–143.
- 33) Saha, R., & Sharma, A. (2016). Primary Delusion and the Sociopolitical Milieu in India - A Case Report & Short Review. *Shanghai Archives of Psychiatry*, 28(4), 230–234. <https://doi.org/10.11919/j.issn.1002-0829.216040>
- 34) Satyanarayana, V. A., Vaddiparti, K., Chandra, P. S., O'Leary, C. C., Benegal, V., & Cottler, L. B. (2010). Problem drinking among married men in India: comparison between husband's and wife's reports. *Drug and Alcohol Review*, 29(5), 557–562. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1465-3362.2010.00177.x>
- 35) Schou, L., & Moan, I. S. (2016). Alcohol use-sickness absence association and the moderating role of gender and socioeconomic status: A literature review. *Drug and Alcohol Review*, 35(2), 158–169. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dar.12278>
- 36) Sharma, N., Sharma, S., Ghai, S., Basu, D., Kumari, D., Singh, D., & Kaur, G. (2016). Living with an alcoholic partner: Problems faced and coping strategies used by wives of alcoholic clients. *Industrial Psychiatry Journal*, 25(1), 65–71. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0972-6748.196053>
- 37) Sontate, K. V., Rahim Kamaluddin, M., Naina Mohamed, I., Mohamed, R. M. P., Shaikh, M. F., Kamal, H., & Kumar, J. (2021). Alcohol, aggression, and violence: From public health to neuroscience. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 699726. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.699726>
- 38) Sreekumar, S., Subhalakshmi, T. P., & Varghese, P. J. (2016). Factors associated with resilience in wives of individuals with alcohol dependence syndrome. *Indian Journal of Psychiatry*, 58(3), 307–310. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0019-5545.192025>
- 39) Stanesby, O., Callinan, S., Graham, K., Wilson, I. M., Greenfield, T. K., Wilsnack, S. C., Hettige, S., Hanh, H. T. M., Siengsounthone, L., Waleewong, O., & Laslett, A. M. (2018). Harm from known others' drinking by relationship proximity to the harmful drinker and gender: A meta-analysis across 10 countries. *Alcoholism, Clinical and Experimental Research*, 42(9), 1693–1703. <https://doi.org/10.1111/acer.13828>
- 40) Stewart, K., Silcock, D., & Wegman, F. (2012). Reducing drink driving in low- and middle-income countries: challenges and opportunities. *Traffic Injury Prevention*, 13(2), 93–95. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15389588.2011.634464>
- 41) The New Indian Express, “Revenue from liquor sales in Kerala touched Rs 35k crore in 2 years”, 28 July 2023,

Impact of Alcoholism of Partner on the Mental Health of Women: Findings from an Exploratory Research

<https://www.newindianexpress.com/states/kerala/2023/Jul/28/revenue-from-liquor-sales-in-kerala-touched-rs-35k-crore-in-2-years-2599304.html#:~:text=LOSS%20OF%20G41.95%20CR,95%20crore.>
Accessed on 25.12.23.

- 42) UN Women, (2020). Issue brief: Covid -19 and ending violence against women and girls. <https://www.unwomen.org/en/digital-library/publications/2020/04/issue-brief-covid-19-and-ending-violence-against-women-and-girls>, accessed on 25.08.2023.
- 43) Valassery, D & Kuruvilla, M. (2018) Dowry and alcoholism as major causes for domestic violence in Kerala. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science (IOSR-JHSS)*, 23 (4), 33-39. Doi: 10.9790/0837-2304053339
- 44) Verma, S., Saharan, A., Polcumpally, A.T., Biswas, M. (2020). Tentacles of COVID-19 in India: Impact on Indian Economy, Society, Polity and Geopolitics. *Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Studies* 2 (3), 54– 61.
- 45) Vora, M., Malathesh, B. C., Das, S., & Chatterjee, S. S. (2020). COVID-19 and domestic violence against women. *Asian Journal of Psychiatry*, 53, 102227. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajp.2020.102227>
- 46) Walker, L. E. (1977). Battered Women and Learned Helplessness. *Victimology* 2 (3-4), 525-534.
- 47) WHO, (2021). Global alcohol action plan 2022-2030 to strengthen implementation of the Global Strategy to Reduce the Harmful Use of Alcohol, Second Draft (Unedited). <https://reviewandmail.co.zw/global-alcohol-conference-set-for-cape-town/> accessed on 20.12.2023.
- 48) Wilson, I. M., Graham, K., Laslett, A. M., & Taft, A. (2020). Relationship trajectories of women experiencing alcohol-related intimate partner violence: A grounded-theory analysis of women's voices. *Social Science & Medicine (1982)*, 264, 113307. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2020.113307>
- 49) Wozniak, J. R., Riley, E. P., & Charness, M. E. (2019). Clinical presentation, diagnosis, and management of fetal alcohol spectrum disorder. *The Lancet. Neurology*, 18(8), 760–770. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422\(19\)30150-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422(19)30150-4)